

DEVELOPMENT OF A REGIONAL PROGRAM FOR THE RECLAMATION OF IRRIGATED LANDS IN A STATE OF DEGRADATION

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the study of issues related to the restoration and introduction of degraded irrigated lands into use in the context of further development and liberalization of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It aims to identify and assess existing problems in this area and to develop certain theoretical and methodological approaches regarding their solutions.*

Keywords: *degradation, economic liberalization, mechanism, land assessment, irrigated lands.*

According to UN data, currently, approximately 6.0 million hectares of land are decertifying worldwide each year. More than 40% of irrigated lands are experiencing degradation due to errors and shortcomings in irrigation and reclamation efforts, rendering them completely unsuitable for crop production and agricultural activities. It is important to remember that land degradation, meaning its deterioration, poses a threat to the living conditions of 1.2 billion people worldwide and to life itself. Climate change and erosion processes are causing an average of 6-7 million hectares of land to be removed from agricultural circulation each year. Today, constructions in the fields of industrial and transport infrastructure, as well as the extraction of underground resources, are creating quarries and soil heaps that are progressively encroaching on agricultural lands. Irrigated lands are being left under the reservoirs being constructed [1].

Similar processes are also occurring in the irrigated areas of our republic. These issues are primarily linked to irrigation-related reclamation construction work in agriculture, where the lithological-geomorphological structure of natural landscapes, hydrogeological and regional-climatic conditions, soil types, and the distinctive characteristics of their reclamation classification are not adequately considered. Additionally, there is a lack of attention to the parameters of collector-drainage systems, and the reclamation and construction activities are being carried out uniformly using a "template" approach.

As of today, over 70% of the irrigated lands in our country have developed a "hydromorph" water regime, where the groundwater level has risen above the critical depth (1-2 meters). The underground flow is either poorly maintained or very weakly supplied. In these areas, processes of salinization, gypsification, and, in some plots, waterlogging have intensified. The water-salt balance has shifted negatively, leading to the accumulation of large reserves of salts in the upper layers.

In recent years, in the irrigated farming zones, especially in the Aral Sea region, various forms of degradation have emerged due to natural conditions and human economic activities—excessive moisture, secondary salinization, desertification, wind and irrigation erosion, pollution with heavy metals and toxic substances, and soil compaction. As a result, the fertility of irrigated soils and crop yields have declined.

Currently, the total irrigated area in our republic is 4,306.8 thousand hectares, with 47.5% (2,045.18 thousand hectares) classified as salinized lands. This includes weakly salinized lands at 31.2% (1,344.7 thousand hectares), moderately salinized soils at 13.63% (587.0 thousand hectares), and strongly salinized soils at 2.6% (113.5 thousand hectares). The total area of salinized lands accounts for 75.8% in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 86.2% in Bukhara region, 80.0% in Jizzakh region, 83.1% in Navoi region, 97.1% in Syrdarya region, and 100% in Khorezm region. Strongly salinized soils are primarily found in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (8.9%) and Khorezm region (12.2%).

In several districts of our republic, among the irrigated crop areas, 30-40%, and in some fields, up to 50% are classified as secondary, strongly salinized lands, affecting cotton seedlings. In some plots, 60-80% of the crops can be lost during the first irrigation. These areas, characterized by "salinity spots," require special agronomic and reclamation measures. However, such measures are not applied; instead, uniform cultivation and fertilization practices are implemented, with yields primarily obtained from the non-salinized portions of the fields.

In addition to the above, negative conditions such as the decline of humus, desertification, waterlogging, pollution, gypsification, encroachment of weeds, contamination, water pressure, and neglect continue to persist in the irrigated lands of our republic. There is currently no systematic and continuous management at any administrative level for monitoring their status, preventing issues, and addressing them. Furthermore, in recent years, there has been little attention given to utilizing advanced technologies to restore degraded lands in irrigated areas.

Importantly, understanding the extent of agricultural product loss and job opportunities due to the degradation of irrigated lands and the failure to generate income is of significant socio-economic importance. According to social surveys conducted with the population, 89% of respondents lack awareness of degraded lands, 78% do not know the causes of land degradation, 86% emphasize the need for government funding for the restoration of degraded lands, and 84% believe that water scarcity contributes to land degradation.

Identifying the causes of these conditions and developing a regional program based on international experiences for monitoring and restoring degraded irrigated lands, along with creating and substantiating a methodology for organizational and economic measures, is considered one of the most pressing issues of our time.

It should be emphasized that in order to deepen the modernization of the economy and improve the implementation of state-targeted programs for the comprehensive development of regions, it is necessary to develop proposals based on the scientific and practical study of these

issues. Creating a methodology for developing a regional program for the reclamation of degraded irrigated lands is essential for both practice and theory.

Improving the regional program for the reclamation of degraded irrigated lands will not only enhance the efficiency of restoring the 270,000 hectares of degraded lands but also help meet the demand for irrigated land in agricultural production. Additionally, it will contribute to the increase in agricultural production volumes, satisfy the growing demand for food products in both domestic and foreign markets, and ensure socio-economic stability.

In conclusion, it is crucial to base the development of a regional program for the reclamation of degraded irrigated lands on studying the characteristics of the regional economy and conducting systematic analysis. This will enable the formulation of scientific and practical proposals and recommendations, as well as an examination of the existing regulatory and legal framework and foreign experiences. Adapting these insights to our republic's context will serve to accelerate the restoration of degraded lands and improve land use practices.

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